

Studies on Oxazoles : Part—II

Synthesis of Some New 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-substituted- Δ^4 -oxazolines and Their Studies as Potential Pesticides

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Some new 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-substituted- Δ^4 -oxazolines, synthesised by condensing various ketones with *sym*-diphenyl urea using bromine as the condensing agent, have been subsequently mercurated with mercuric acetate to yield respective 2-arylimino-3-(*p*-acetoxy mercuric phenyl)-4-substituted- Δ^4 -oxazolines which have been assayed for their pesticidal character against *Piricularia oryzae* (Cav.) and *Helminthosporium oryzae*, the causative organism of rice blast as the test fungi and *S. aureus* and *E. coli* as the test bacteria. A relation between biocidal character and chemical structure has been explored.

In view of the prodigious range of activity of the oxazole class of compounds, their synthesis has been extensively studied. Recently a large number of pharmaceutical applications of oxazoles like sedative¹, spasmolytic², central nervous system depressant³, cardiac stimulant⁴, antihistaminic, muscle relaxant and hypotensive⁵ have been reported. Particularly, oxazoline derivatives have been of interest because of their plant growth regulating activity⁶ as well as their antibacterial⁷ and antifungal⁸ character.

Halogens like bromine have been successfully used as a condensing agent in the synthesis of thiazoles and thiazolines⁹. Because of many advantages of this method, the same has been employed in the synthesis of oxazoles¹⁰. In continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis of new oxazole derivatives for use as potential fungicides and antibacterials¹⁰, the present paper describes the preparation of some new 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-substituted- Δ^4 -oxazolines. These oxazolines have been prepared by condensing ten different ketones with *sym*-diphenyl urea in presence of bromine and dry benzene.

It has been assumed that the oxazoline(I) is formed as a result of the reaction of ketone and the *sym*-diphenyl urea through their enol-forms with bromine as shown below :

Other possible course of reaction has been investigated. The possibility of nuclear bromination

has been precluded by the absence of bromine in the final product (I), $R=C_6H_5-$. The reaction product has also been shown not to contain even a trace of 2-anilinobenzoxazole, another possible way for the condensation reaction. That the reaction proceeds through the intermediate formation of α -halo ketones has been verified by the fact that the oxazoline-(I), $R=C_6H_5-$ from the reaction of acetophenone, bromine and *sym*-diphenyl urea was found to be identical with the product of the reaction of phenacyl bromide with *sym*-diphenyl urea. This modified reaction has the advantage that it dispenses with the use of relatively inaccessible and costlier α -halo ketones and also a fairly good yield of oxazoline is obtained. The homogeneity and purity of the oxazoline have been tested through tlc.

The structure-(I) for oxazoline is supported and confirmed by its acid hydrolysis to oxazolone(II) and aniline.

When aromatic amines¹¹ and 2-phenyl imino-3-phenyl-4-substituted thiazolines¹² are mercurated the monoacetoxy mercuri-derivatives are formed, the acetoxy mercuri group entering the para-position of the $-\text{NH}_2$ in the aromatic amine and the para-position of the 3-aryl nucleus of the thiazolines. If the para-position is not free, the acetoxy mercuri-group enters the ortho-positions of the aryl nucleus. Hence, in the present series, the acetoxy mercuri group has been assumed to have entered the para-position of the 3-aryl nucleus of the oxazolines as shown (III). This assumption has been further supported by the fact that when (III) is treated with potassium perbromide, a mono bromo derivative (IV) which on acidic hydrolysis gives the bromo compound(V). V is identical with the acid hydrolysis product from oxazoline(VI), obtained by the condensation of acetophenone with *sym.* di-*p*-bromophenyl urea as usual. The identity of the two compounds is confirmed through their same m.p., m.m.p. and R_f values on tlc.

Experimental

1. 2-Phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-substituted- Δ^4 -oxazoline :

To a solution of acetophenone (2.4 g) in benzene (10 ml), bromine (3.2 g) in dry benzene (30 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. When the reaction was complete, *sym*-diphenyl urea (4.25 g) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 30 hr, the solvent distilled off, the product

trituated with ether overnight. The ether decanted off, the residue boiled with water and the water was decanted hot. Basification with strong ammonia gave a gum which gradually solidified. The product was crystallized from ethanol acidified with acetic acid.

The yield, m.p., analytical data and the fungicidal activity of such 2-aryl imino-3-aryl-4-substituted- Δ^4 -oxazolines are given in Table 1.

2. 2-Phenylimino-3-(*p*-acetoxy mercuric phenyl)-4-phenyl- Δ^4 -oxazoline :

The oxazoline (1 g) in acetic acid-ethanol (1 : 1) (10 ml) was treated with a solution of mercuric acetate (1.6 g) in 0.1 (*N*) acetic acid (20 ml). The mixture was stirred well and left overnight at room temperature. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed repeatedly with hot water, dilute alcohol and dilute acetic acid. The m.p., analytical data and the pesticidal results of the acetoxy mercuri derivatives are given in Table 1.

Fungicidal Test : The oxazolines and their acetoxy mercuri derivatives have been assayed for their fungicidal character by the method of Montgomery and Moore¹³, with slight modification. *P. oryzae* (Cav.), *H. oryzae*, the causative organism of rice blast have been used as the test fungi. The spores were kept in contact with the compounds at different dilutions for 24 hr at 25° and the percentage of germination was studied. The dilution in ppm of the compounds for 50 per cent. germina-

TABLE-I

Nature of R	Yield %	M.L.P. °C	%N		Fungicidal activity in ppm for 50% germination		Bactericidal activity minimum inhibitory conc.	
			Found	Calc.	<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1. C ₆ H ₅ -	65	189	9.15	9.29	2.5	3.0	1 : 20,000	1 : 20,000
2. (<i>p</i>)-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	70	215	8.12	8.08	0.5	1.0	"	"
3. (<i>p</i>)-OH.C ₆ H ₄ -	55	192	8.48	8.53	2.1	2.1	"	"
4. β -C ₁₀ H ₇ -	56	195	7.70	7.73	1.0	2.0	"	"
5. (<i>p</i>)-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	62	205	8.36	8.43	2.5	3.0	"	"
6. (<i>p</i>)-OC ₂ H ₅ - C ₆ H ₄ -	65	210	7.78	7.86	3.5	4.25	"	"
7. CH ₃ -	57	222	11.12	11.20	4.5	4.2	"	"
8. (<i>p</i>)-NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ -	72	195	11.72	11.76	3.0	3.5	"	"
9. (<i>p</i>)-CH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	55	201	8.51	8.53	2.0	2.5	"	"
10. C ₄ H ₉ S -	56	160	8.78	8.80	2.1	2.5	"	"
11. 2-C ₆ H ₅ -	-	>250	35.02	35.15*	1.0	1.4	1 : 100,000	1 : 100,000
12. (<i>p</i>)-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	-	>250	33.03	33.15*	0.3	0.5	"	"
13. (<i>p</i>)-OH - C ₆ H ₄ -	-	220	34.06	34.19*	0.5	1.0	"	"
14. β -C ₁₀ H ₇ -	-	>250	32.15	32.32*	0.5	1.0	"	"
15. (<i>p</i>)-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	-	240d	33.25	33.39*	1.0	2.0	1 : 40,000	1 : 40,000
16. (<i>p</i>)-OC ₂ H ₅ - C ₆ H ₄ -	-	>250	32.52	32.63*	1.0	1.4	"	"
17. CH ₃ -	-	>250	39.23	39.44*	1.3	2.0	"	"
18. (<i>p</i>)-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ -	-	225	32.47	32.58*	1.4	2.0	"	"
19. (<i>p</i>)-CH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	-	245d	34.21	34.31*	1.0	1.0	1 : 100,000	1 : 100,000
20. 2-C ₆ H ₅ S -	-	235d	34.66	34.77*	0.5	1.0	"	"

R' = H for compounds 1 to 10 and R' = Hg.OOC.CH₃ for compounds 11 to 20
(d) = decomposition, * denotes percentage of mercury.

tion of the fungus has been given in Table 1. The following generalisations in respect of the fungicidal results may be made :

- (1) In oxazolines, the nature of substituents at position-4 has a marked effect on the two test fungi, i.e., *P. oryzae* and *H. oryzae*.
- (2) The presence of chlorine in the molecule confers maximum fungicidal action on both the fungi.
- (3) Toxophoric group like, $C_{10}H_7$ — inhibits the growth of *P. oryzae* at a lower concentration, but in the case of *H. oryzae* the activity is less.
- (4) Substituent like, C_6H_5 —, $p-OH-C_6H_4$ —, $p-OCH_3-C_6H_4$ —, $p-CH_3-C_6H_4$ — and C_4H_9S — cause no remarkable change in the fungicidal activity, (range of activity remains between 2 to 3 ppm for 50 per cent. germination for both the fungi) whereas, groups like NO_2 —, CH_3 — and $OC_2H_5-C_6H_4$ — has inactivating effect.
- (5) The fungicidal action of the mono-acetoxy mercuri derivative of oxazolines on both the fungi is greater than the non-mercurated one.

Bactericidal Test :

The bactericidal test was done by Rideal-Walker Serial Drop dilution method¹⁴. The antibacterial activity against two test bacteria, *S. aureus* and *E. coli* has been studied. For this purpose, the BDH beef extract was used for the preparation of nutrient broth. The compounds were kept in contact with the bacteria for 10 minutes. The time of incubation of the test organism was 24 hr at 35°. The antibacterial activity has been shown in term of M.E.D. The oxazolines have been found to inhibit the growth of the bacteria at 1 : 20,000 dilution. The bactericidal action of the mono-acetoxy mercuri derivatives of the oxazolines on both the bacteria is more than the non-mercurated one. The substituents like $p-Cl-C_6H_4$ —, $C_{10}H_7$ —, $p-OH-C_6H_4$ —, $p-CH_3-C_6H_4$ — and C_4H_9S — at position-4 of the mercurated

oxazolines confer maximum bactericidal activity as these compounds inhibit the bacterial growth at 1 : 100,000 dilution.

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